

The effects of a fracking ban in the United States

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Solvency

Empirically, the US and the EPA do not have a good track record of enforcing environmental regulations. In regards to environmental issues, a report from EHN finds: “Even where federal regulations do exist, meaningful enforcement has been lacking.” [1]

Furthermore, EPA resources are limited, and implementing new plans like this can substantially hinder the EPA's ability to solve for issues.[2] To implement a ban of fracking it would be necessary to hire new workforce in order to shut down fracking sites, and the EPA would face many lawsuits. This will not only harm the EPA's ability to enforce fracking bans, but also other programs. The same goes for other agencies that might have a role in enforcing the ban such as BLM as well .

Economy and generational poverty

Many people's jobs are dependent upon the fracking industry.

Fracking is essential to the economy of the US, and it has added over 725,000 jobs.[3] In a country with under 160M workers this means that fracking accounts for about 0.5% of all jobs in the country. But that is just direct jobs, in total fracking “supports 9.8 million jobs or 5.6 percent of total U.S. employment.”[4]

Unemployment leads to generational poverty

This is a major factor to consider before banning fracking because job loss causes mass poverty. [5] This poverty carries over to future generations because the effects of poverty can cause physiological problems that affect decision making skills necessary to lift oneself out of poverty, poor schools have a harder time of preparing students for life beyond highschool, many students face abuse at home that can hinder their development and education, but abuse can also occur at school “leaving a student in a no-win situation;” and in the end students from poor families in impoverished communities “suffer from the same things that affect their parents.”[6]

Summary

By banning fracking, we kill an industry that 9.8 million people depend on for jobs, and risk sending their families, and future generations of those employed now into a vicious cycle of generational poverty.

Alternative energy

Shifting away from fracking creates a coal revival

Forcing the shift away from fracking before renewables are ready will revive coal which is worse. [7] Coal emits far more SO₂, NO_x, and CO₂. [8] Of course everybody is aware of the effects that carbon dioxide has on the atmosphere, and climate change. This in and of itself would be a devastating effect of the coal revival, but specifically increased sulfur dioxide emissions would have a devastating effect on the environment and people.

Asthma and death caused by SO₂

Within recent history, one of the main sources of sulfur pollution was marine vessels, and this source alone accounted for hundreds of thousands of deaths, and millions of asthma cases in children . “Low-sulphur limits for marine fuels reduces ship air pollution and attributable health impacts substantially. Prior to cleaner ship fuels, ship-related health impacts include ~400,000 premature deaths from lung cancer and cardiovascular disease and ~ 14 million childhood asthma cases annually. ”[\[9\]](#)

Acid rain

SO₂ is the cause of acid rain.[\[10\]](#) The effects of acid rain are devastating, especially in terms of aquatic ecosystems. With lower PH levels caused by acid rain fish eggs cannot hatch, and adult fish die. Furthermore, the effects of acid rain on land are also devastating. Acid rain destroys soil and kills trees.[\[11\]](#)

Food insecurity

The immediate effect of acid rain would be causing food insecurity because it is impossible to grow crops when the soil has been destroyed. Furthermore, the biodiversity loss caused by SO₂ would also cause food insecurity on a massive scale, and biodiversity loss is a leading cause of food insecurity.[\[12\]](#)

This food insecurity is a major problem, and really the ultimate impact. “We have a strong obligation to aid the starving even if we would eventually become malnourished. On this view,

to survive on lifeboat earth, knowing that others were tossed overboard into the sea of starvation, would signify an indignity and callousness worse than extinction. It would be morally preferable to die struggling to create a decent life for all than to continue to live at the expense of the starving.”[13]

Fracking can solve for all of this

Fracking enables the shift to renewables. This is because renewables can not be implemented within the next decade. But an energy source is still needed in the intermittency. Fracking is a good source of energy because of its relatively low emissions. [14] Furthermore fracking does not emit SO₂, and because of this it doesn't cause asthma or lung cancer. Acid rain also is not a problem meaning that ocean biodiversity is preserved, and the soil is not affected by acid rain either; and thus the impact of food insecurity does not occur if we do not ban fracking.

Global security

Banning fracking enables Russian expansionism

Current US liquid natural gas (LNG) exports assures US energy leadership, but banning fracking would upend this. [15] This is a major problem because LNG exports are the main tool that the US currently has to influence Russia. [16] Banning fracking not only prevents the US from engaging with Russia, but also the EU. This is because the EU is dependent on Russia and the US for LNG imports [17], so a decrease in US exports allows for Russian energy blackmail of the EU.[18] This energy diversity currently present within Europe is the only thing preventing

Russian invasion of the baltic states.[19] Furthermore, an invasion of the baltic states is Putin's dream. [20]

Consequences of a Baltics invasion

Upon invasion of the baltics there are two possibilities. 1. Nothing happens. Or 2. NATO retaliates with military action. This first possibility is probably the most likely scenario, but that is not necessarily a good thing. Many human rights issues exist in Russia including torture, imprisonment of political candidates, targeted campaigns against NGOs, oppression of freedom of speech, persecution of religious groups, persecution of human rights defenders, persecution of environmental activists, persecution based on race, and persecution based on sexual and gender identity.[21] So, upon invasion of the baltic states these human rights violations are spread to millions of people, and this is exactly the reason we need to stop Russian expansionism, but in practice this may be even worse.

Alternate scenario risks nuclear war

An invasion of the Baltics could draw NATO in because of the mutual defense agreement present within the Washington Treaty, and "there is a possibility that if Russian forces are sufficiently degraded or defeated in Kaliningrad that Moscow may resort to or threaten nuclear first use." "Such a war will almost certainly escalate into a full-up nuclear war between the planet's only two nuclear superpowers—which means everyone loses." [22] Nuclear models prove that situations like this lead to complete planetary extinction.[23]

Summary

The EU is dependent on Russian and US LNG imports, and LNG is a key tool that Biden has to influence Russia. Banning fracking kills these exports meaning the EU is opened up to energy blackmail, and the US loses leverage with Russia. This leverage that the US has along with EU energy diversity is the only thing preventing Putin from invading the Baltic states — something which he wants to do very much. If this invasion happens either NATO does not retaliate and millions are left to deal with vast human rights abuses, or NATO engages in a war with Russia over the issue risking nuclear war and extinction. Either way we are left with a no win situation if the Baltics are invaded, and we see that deterrence is key.

Lesser action

There are actions that can be taken that do not ban fracking, and do not risk the listed disadvantages, but still solve for potential issues. The USFG pass legislation reforming section 1421(d) of the SDWA, ending the Halliburton Loophole and removing the exemption for fracking from the SDWA.

The Halliburton loophole is a provision in the Safe Drinking Water Act which exempts fracking from EPA regulation. This means that fracking companies do not have to disclose, or comply with EPA limits on harmful chemicals or dangerous practices. [24] Research shows that some of the chemicals used in the fracking process are harmful in certain quantities, but research is limited and more needs to be done to obtain conclusive results for many chemicals. [25] Because fracking companies are not required to disclose their hydraulic fracturing fluid solutions

there are serious gaps in the research. Through amending the SDWA, it will force fracking companies to disclose their hydraulic fracturing fluid solution, and force them to comply with EPA safety standards. The EPA will also conduct research of their own. This data is important for risk mitigation [26], and risk mitigation is key to prevent fracking accidents. [27]

By taking less drastic action, it is possible to mitigate potential risks while preserving jobs, preventing pollution from coal and the impacts that come along with that such as food insecurity, biodiversity loss, and food insecurity; and without risking the US' position in regards to national security and Russia.

Summary

If fracking is banned, there will be severe impacts. 9.8 million people rely on the fracking industry for jobs, and this will launch many families into a devastating cycle of generational poverty. Forcing the shift away from fracking before renewables can replace it will revive coal, and this is far worse. Coal releases SO₂ which causes 400,000 deaths due to lung cancer, and millions of childhood asthma cases. Additionally it causes acid rain which destroys aquatic biodiversity, and soil leading to food insecurity which is the ultimate moral impact. Fracking is also the main leverage the US has against Russia, and without this leverage Russia will invade the Baltics, and either human rights abuses will be spread to millions, or a war will ensue between Russia and NATO with the possibility of escalating to an extinction level nuclear war.

There is no reason to risk any of this because we can implement less radical plans that focus on risk mitigation, and can solve for spills, and change the chemical composition of possibly toxic hydraulic fracturing fluid. When we have this simple alternative, there is absolutely no justifiable reason to ban fracking.

Endnotes

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